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DELIVERABLE REPORT

WP18 Bridging academic and industrial research

D18.3

First report on Outreach, Awareness and Engagement to industrial community

Due date

M18

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First report on outreach, awareness and engagement to industrial community

DELIVERABLE DESCRIPTION

This is the first report on outreach, awareness and engagement to industrial community. It proposes a follow up of the activities that have been carried out until M18 in the framework of Task 18.2 dedicated to the outreach to industrial community as part of WP18 "Bridging academic and industrial research".

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NATURE

- R - Report
- P - Prototype
- DEC - Websites, Patent filing, Press & media actions, Videos, etc
- O - Other

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

- P - Public
- PP - Restricted to other programme participants & EC: (Specify)
- RE - Restricted to a group (Specify)
- CO - Confidential, only for members of the consortium

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CONTENTS

1 Executive Summary	5
2 Premises	5
2.1 Context	5
2.2 Objectives	5
2.3 Industry involvement	6
2.4 Outreach strategy	6
3 Dissemination	7
3.1 Marketing campaign	7
3.2 Events attendance	9
3.3 EIC Ecosystem Partnership	9
3.4 Virtual booth	10
3.5 Business meetings campaign	10
3.6 ICONet	10
4 Next steps	11
4.1 Event attendance	11
4.2 Marketing campaign	11

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report is a deliverable of Task 18.2 dedicated to the outreach to industrial community as part of WP18 "Bridging academic and industrial research". This report proposes a follow up of the activities that have been carried out in the framework of WP until M18. It follows a marketing and dissemination campaign that has started in April, just after the outreach strategy report (D18.2) have been issued at M13. This report includes the main objectives of the outreach activities, the activities that have been implemented so far and some guidelines about how to improve the future campaign and foster innovation.

It will cover the different topics:

- THE CONTEXT, OBJECTIVES, CURRENT KPI AND THE ONGOING MARKETING STRATEGY
- THE FOLLOW UP ABOUT MARKETING, OUTREACH AND DISSEMINATION
- GOOD PRACTISES AND NEXT STEPS FOR UPGRADED OUTREACH CAMPAIGN

2 PREMISES

2.1 Context

The main goal of NFFA-Europe-Pilot (NEP) is to foster innovation and enhance European competitiveness in nanoscience and nano-to-micro analysis and nanotechnology. The uniqueness of NEP is to offer, to a broad academic user community and to industry/SMEs, combined access to state-of-the-art tools in nanoscience and nano-to-micro analysis available in Europe. The PILOT project builds on the success of the NFFA-Europe INFRAIA-1-2014-2015 action. During the NFFA-Europe project (2015 - 2021) there have been 15 calls, 321 proposal were accepted and the number of accepted industrial proposal has reached 11.5%. The rate of acceptance was 65%. This number is higher than the objective initially set which was 5%. For NEP campaign, 16 quarterly calls are scheduled along 5 years (accounting for the access deferral periods needed at the beginning and at the end of the project).

2.2 Objectives

NEP has raised its ambition compared to NFFA-Europe by raising the objective of accepted proposals with industry involvement to 7%. The estimated number of projects over the 5 years is 420. According to the outreach strategy report (D18.2), to fulfill the 7% industry engagement, the estimated number of industrial projects accepted has to be 32 and the estimated number of submitted proposals has to be at least 49 with a rate of acceptance of 65% (NFFA-Europe). It means, at least 3 industrial proposals have to be submitted at each call or 12 by year (4 calls). The marketing and dissemination plan have been established to honor this KPI.

2.3 Industry involvement

In total, for the first 3 calls, 122 proposals have been submitted via the peer-review access. 14 of them are involved with industry which represents 11% of all the research projects submitted. This number is higher with the objective of 7% which is a good sign of attractiveness of NFFA research infrastructure to the industry.

However, this KPI can be improved. One of the major goals is to get more proposals from industrials. Most of the industry involvement comes from Public Private Partnership (PPPs) and the aim is to have more industrial proposals coming directly from companies. Developing a high impact network and raise awareness could help in engaging with these potential industrial PIs.

2.4 Outreach strategy

The outreach strategy has been defined on the deliverable D18.2.

Audience

- SMEs
- Large companies
- PPPs
- Technological clusters
- Potential partners

Communication channels

- Website articles
- Email marketing
- Social networks
- YouTube

Offline marketing

- Business events attendance
- B2B meetings

Supporting materials

- Roll up
- Posters
- Flyers
- Business card
- Leaflets
- Powerpoint presentation

3 DISSEMINATION

3.1 Marketing campaign

Supporting materials

In close collaboration with Promoscience, a rollup has been designed to fit with the expectations of industrials.

- The upper section is dedicated to the main market sectors where NFFA could be relevant to apply for an industrial.
- A clear message: "free access for industry" has been displayed to attract the potential industrial users.
- The 4 steps process has been shown in a way that is easy to understand and is not scary for the future user.
- The European map locating the partners is displayed on the bottom

The rollup is divided into several sections:

- Top Header:** "for your project" (orange) and "at the nano- & the microscale" (blue).
- Sectors:** Six panels showing "SOLAR ENERGY", "AEROSPACE", "NANO MEDICINE", "NANO ELECTRONICS", "BATTERY", and "QUANTUM TECHNOLOGY".
- Logo:** The NFFA logo, consisting of stylized letters in orange and blue.
- Central Message:** "FREE ACCESS FOR INDUSTRY" with the hashtag "#Nanotechnology".
- 4-Step Process:**
 - 1 BROWSE & CHOOSE:** visit www.nffa.eu, browse the offer & select the tools you need.
 - 2 SUBMIT YOUR PROPOSAL:** on our single-entry point.
 - 3 HAVE IT EVALUATED:** and ranked by an international peer-review panel.
 - 4 GET FREE ACCESS:** and receive a contribution for travel & subsistence costs.
- QR Code:** A QR code linking to www.nffa.eu.
- Network of Expertise:** "A NETWORK OF OUTSTANDING EXPERTISE" with "44 state of the art facilities across Europe".
- Map:** A map of Europe showing the locations of the network's facilities.
- Logos:** The European Union flag, the Horizon 2020 logo, and the NFFA logo with the text "nffa.eu RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE".

Figure 1: rollup for industry

Powerpoint Presentation

The powerpoint presentation provided by Promoscience has been updated to better fit the need of industrials. It is structured as followed:

1. Presentation of NFFA-Europe / NEP
2. Case studies/market segmentation
3. Portfolio of techniques
4. Easy 4 step process

LinkedIn campaign

A linkedIn campaign has been set up in close collaboration with Promoscience to provide a smooth editorial line well balanced between the two audience: academics and industry.

We have chosen to publish post per month, below is a recap of published posts:

- 2 posts about study case
- 1 post about the different installation
- 1 post about IndTech event

Here are the following pictures that were used and were designed by the NFFA business developer in collaboration with Promoscience.

Figure 2: LinkedIn post: Study case 1

Figure 3: LinkedIn post: Study case 2

Figure 4: LinkedIn post: portfolio of techniques

Figure 5: LinkedIn post: event

Regularly, new contacts with strategic entities are made through LinkedIn and a private message is sent to invite them for a discussion about micro- and nanotechnologies with the aim to raise awareness by organizing a B2B meeting to introduce the distributed research infrastructure.

Email marketing

Regularly, email marketing are sent to valuable contacts that could be interested about submitting a proposal. The type of companies targeted are SMEs. For the contacts, we aim at CEO, CTO or innovation representative.

Around 50 email marketing has been sent to innovative SMEs in micro- & -nanotechnologies in the domain of solar energy and nanoelectronics. 6 B2B meetings has been scheduled to raise awareness about NFFA-Europe.

A work has been done to design an impactful corporate email banner and email signature.

The picture on the signature is changed accordingly with the sector of market of the contact to reach.

Figure 6: email banner

3.2 Events attendance

The following events has been attended:

1. KFS Transfer Workshop, 28th-29th of April, Berlin
2. Minalogic Business Meetings, 31st of May (B2B meetings), Grenoble
3. EIC webinar with participants of pathfinder projects, 7th of June, Zoom
4. Leti Innovation Days 21st-23rd of June (B2B meetings scheduled), Grenoble
5. IndTech2022 28th-30th of June (Booth), Grenoble

At the exception of KFS Transfer Workshop where Uwe Sassenberg from DESY was present, the other events were attended by the NFFA business developer based at the ESRF.

3.3 EIC Ecosystem Partnership

EIC ecosystem Partnership is an initiative to boost business opportunities and catalyse the access to breakthrough technologies for EIC beneficiaries. It provides service such as participation to business events and access to EIC beneficiaries portfolio. This could be a great opportunity for NFFA to join this such initiative as it could bring potential industrial users and have a high business impact.

In collaboration with the NFFA management team, an application has been filed and we are waiting for an answer from EIC. If the outcome is negative, a revised application should be filed by the end of the year.

3.4 Virtual booth

A one year virtual booth has been ordered on the MatCharExpo website (https://www.matcharexpo.net/nffa_europe/). The objective is to diversify the outreach actions to better engage with industry. It is set as experimentation to understand if these initiatives are impactful. The duration is one year and should be extended if the results in terms of new prospects/contacts are satisfactory.

3.5 Business meetings campaign

- During and following the 3 events attendance **40 B2B meetings** has been organized, either with clusters, spinoffs, large companies or others.
- Following the email marketing campaign **6 B2B meetings** has been organized.
- Finally, **2 B2B meetings** have been organized thanks to the LinkedIn campaign.
- In total, **48 B2B meetings** has been organized during the period April - July

As most of the meetings are organized with SMEs, a specific is made on incentives like the free-of-charge peer-review access, the confidentiality access and the technical consultancy. Following these meetings, contact have been established or discussion are ongoing. Either they are interested for submitting a proposal, joining the consortium by applying to the next call for new providers or act as multiplier to spread information about our research infrastructure. In total, 6 have shown interest in submitting and discussion have started. In total, 2 companies are interested in joining the consortium by applying to the next call for new providers.

3.6 ICONet

Among the NEP project, ICONet is a pilot network of the industrial and commercial offices of the providers (ICONet) as an ad-hoc solution for facilitating industrial and SME access. Such a network is already in place at most of the member facilities. The main goal is to provide a dedicated intermediation service, which will exploit, coordinate and rationalize the competence available in the different Industrial Contact Office (ICOs) often already present at member facilities. This ICOs network (ICONet) contributes to understanding and translating the needs expressed by the industrial user and identifying the most appropriate technique to answer the need. Furthermore, the ICONet accompany the industrial users for the access preparation and, when relevant, help to identify academic partners, among the NFFA user community, to collaborate with the industrial user in order to make the access even more effective.

2 kick off meetings were scheduled with the local node to present and validate the marketing strategy. In the specific case, large companies are interested in proprietary access ICONet gathered for taking part to the discussions as it represents a great opportunity for the consortium. In order

to start discussions with local clusters and European initiatives that could act as multipliers, ICONet is a great asset to facilitate the first contact.

4 NEXT STEPS

4.1 Event attendance

- France Innovation 20th of September Virtual
- RDV Carnot 12th – 13th of October Paris, France
- Tech Innov March 2023
- Minalogic Business Meetings May 2023
- SPIE Photonics Europe 2023
- Meet4Hydrogen (if organized)
- SEMICON (2023 or 2024)

4.2 Marketing campaign

To improve NFFA action toward industry, some activities need to be implemented or to be continued. Below here, is the list of actions considered as important to keep track to go forward:

- Send an email to previous industrial users to organize B2B meetings
- Send an email to the companies that have applied to be an industrial partner among NFFA-Europe consortium and have not succeed to propose them to join business strategic council
- Continue the linkedIn campaign with one post per month
- Continue the email marketing campaign and event attendance with the objective of at least 10 B2B meetings scheduled by month.

